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Abstract: Business plan makers are faced with the task of selecting available communication channels. This article discusses the two types of communication channels: personal communication channels and non-personal communication channels, and how to properly organize marketing through these channels.

Keywords: expert, evaluation channel, social-consumer channel, target buyers, high-value, high-risk, product.

КОММУНИКАЦИЯ В МАРКЕТИНГЕ

Аннотация: Составители бизнес-планов сталкиваются с задачей выбора доступных каналов коммуникации. В этой статье всесторонне рассматриваются два типа каналов коммуникации: каналы личной коммуникации и каналы неличной коммуникации, а также правильная организация маркетинга через эти каналы.

Ключевые слова: эксперт, канал оценки, социально-потребительский канал, целевые покупатели, высокая ценность, высокий риск, продукт.

MARKETINGDA KOMMUNIKATSIYA

Annotatsiya: Biznes rejani tuzuvchilar oldida mavjud kommunikatsiya kanallarini tanlash vazifasi turadi. Ushbu maqolada yaxlit holda kommunikatsiya kanallari ikki ko'rinishdaxsiy kommunikatsiya kanallari va shaxsiy bo'lmagan kommunikatsiya kanallari bo'lishi,shu kanallar orqali marketingni to'g'ri tashkillashtirish yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ekspert, baholash kanali, ijtimoiy-iste'molchi kanali, maqsadli xaridorlar, yuqori qiymatli, yuqori xavf, mahsulot.

Introduction. The main task of marketing is to identify the needs and wants of each market and select those among them that the company can provide a superior service to its competitors. This allows the company to produce high-quality products and, as a result, increase the company's overall profit by satisfying the needs of consumers.

The main directions of comprehensive market research based on marketing are:

- demand research;
- market structure determination;
- product research;
- competitive analysis;
- sales forms and methods analysis.

Business planners are faced with the task of selecting available communication channels. In general, communication channels come in two forms: personal communication channels and impersonal communication channels.

Personal communication channels involve two or more individuals who communicate directly with each other. Personal communication channels are effective because they allow participants to make personal appeals and establish feedback. Personal communication channels can be further divided into promotional, expert evaluation, and social channels.

The promotional channel involves the company's sales staff who communicate with customers in the target market.

The expert evaluation channel is formed by independent individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills. The main drivers of the social-consumer channel are neighbors, friends, family members, and colleagues who are in conversation with target buyers. This channel is known as a somewhat more active one in most product areas. Personal influence plays a significant role in making purchases in high-value and high-risk product categories. Buyers of cars and large household appliances do not limit themselves to referring to mass media sources, but also seek to know the opinions of people who know the industry. First of all, personal influence plays an important role in relation to products that are of interest to many. Non-personal communication channels are a means of transmitting (sending) information in the absence of personal contact (interaction) and feedback. Advertising is a form of promoting, on behalf of a certain sponsor, goods or services in the mass media for a certain fee.

Advertising is one of the largest industries in Uzbekistan industry. Uzbek companies spend much money on advertising their products. Since advertising is aimed at consumers and is intended to influence their decisions about their behavior in the consumer market, it is useful to get acquainted with the services provided by advertising and its organization. Advertising serves the interests of consumers and economists, because it informs consumers about prices and the latest news in the commodity market. Advertising often leads to a decrease in prices. Advertising creates a mass market, which allows manufacturers to reduce costs. This saving is used by consumers. Advertising stimulates competition, which benefits consumers and society as a whole. Through the advertising of one company, all other enterprises in the network strive for at least the same level of quality. Advertising revenue covers a large part of the costs of magazines and newspapers, the entire cost of commercial radio and TV. Advertising stimulates consumer demand and benefits the economy as a whole. The harm of advertising to society. Many people do not believe that advertising is beneficial to society; The following can be listed as disadvantages of advertising, namely, advertising often provides incorrect information and confuses buyers. Advertising requires large financial costs, which increases the cost of goods. It causes consumers to spend money on goods that they do not really need. The mass media become dependent on advertisers, which limits their freedom.

The most common types of advertising strategies are: appeals, appeals to reason, and appeals to emotion. This advertising often uses meaningless or completely meaningless rhetoric: "If you want to produce a printed product, contact "Sharq". "Sharq" is the leader of printers!" This statement can fool no one, "Sharq" is not a leader. But such appeals are based on the idea that if they are repeated many times, they will not fail to affect buyers.

Conclusion. Marketing is a process that involves planning and implementing the process of pricing, selling, and distributing ideas/products/services to meet and convert the goals of specific individuals or enterprises. The marketing plan involves assessing the enterprise's product sales markets and competitors and justifying the marketing strategy. The marketing plan is also necessary for the internal organization of the enterprise and is the basis for communication with partners and investors.

The marketing plan covers issues such as the distribution scheme of manufactured products, pricing methods, product policy, and product design.

When developing a marketing plan, it is necessary to ensure maximum adaptation of production to market requirements and active influence on the market and consumers using available tools

(product quality, advertising, service, etc.). It is necessary to demonstrate that the enterprise is able to deliver its products to the consumer. During the process of developing a business plan, a marketing plan requires addressing many questions that require detailed development.

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